

LANGUAGE OF COMMUNICATION AS MEANS OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation

Language is a linguistic technique used by everyone in their daily life as a means to convey information and arguments to others. Language is the prime medium of communication. Above all, the primary purpose of a language is, making our challenging and complex thoughts easier. This article focuses on the role of language in the social life of human being, culture and society.

Key words

Language, linguistics, signs, speech, communication, consciousness, sociolinguistic difference, community, system

Аннотация

Язык – является средством общения используемое каждым человеком в повседневной жизни как средство передачи информации и аргументов другим людям. Язык является основным средством общения. Прежде всего, основная цель языка – облегчить наши сложные мысли. В данной статье основное внимание уделяется роли языка в социальной жизни человека, культуре и обществе.

Ключевые слова

язык, лингвистика, знаки, речь, общение, сознание, социолингвистическое различие, общность, система

Annotatsiya

Til har bir inson tomonidan kundalik hayotda boshqa odamlarga ma'lumot va dalillarni uzatish vositasi sifatida foydalanadigan aloqa vositasidir. Avvalo, asosiy til asosiy tildir. Bu davlatda shaxs, madaniyat va jamiyatning til va ijtimoiy hayotining o'riniga asosiy e'tibor beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar

til, tilshunoslik, til, til, jamiyat, tushunish, sotsiolingvistik farqlar, jamiyat, tizim.

A necessary condition for the existence of society is the presence of language. Language is the most important and basic means of communication, a necessary condition for the material and spiritual existence of a person. Areas of language use

permeate all spheres of social space: language is inseparable from any manifestations of human social life

In modern linguistics, language is recognized as a complex system of signs. In the functioning of language, its signs are not arbitrary; they are stable and changeable - depending on the needs of society and consciousness. The signs of language as elements of its system are fused with the system of consciousness, and through it - with the system of social life of people. Language signs admit of structural and functional typology.

The signs of language have stability, which is explained not by their social nature, but by the stability of society, its labor skills, social institutions, the laws of consciousness and the results achieved by its development. Society is interested in the stability of the language, which ensures the possibility of mutual understanding among team members and the continuity of moral, labor and other experience, its transmission from one generation to another.

Language is different from all other social institutions and cannot be changed at the will of statesmen or scientists. It is too complex, and it is subject to the universal tradition of its use, since it is needed by everyone and for all types of human activity. Language is included in all spheres of social existence and forms of social consciousness, which gives it a supra-class and supra-group character. Language is the most important integrator of society. It is in language that the social structure of society and the sociolinguistic differences in the speech practices of speakers are reflected.

Language is a phenomenon of spiritual culture, one of the forms of social consciousness: language helps to transmit the social experience of humanity (cultural traditions, norms, scientific knowledge).

The role of language is unique: linguistic changes lead to the improvement of language as a means of communication and cognition; its changes are determined by the development of society, its material and spiritual culture. The development of writing led to an increase in the communicative capabilities of the language and to the formation of a new type of speech - written speech.

The role of language as a means of communication in the life of society is increasing: as a result of the development of communication channels and the intellectualization of production, the scope of use and scope of functions of language are expanding.

Language is realized and exists in speech, which ensures that a person is included in the society of his own kind. Speech is the process of using language to

communicate between people. Language and speech are inextricably linked and represent a unity.

Speech contacts between people can have different motivations: it can be general information, an application for intellectual communication, establishing or strengthening interpersonal contacts, emotional release, etc. Regardless of the motives for which a person enters into communication, his speech characteristics are often decisive for career advancement and the acquisition of authority in society.

High speech indicators of a person depend on his ability to speak in accordance with the requirements for the spoken word: they relate to the structure of speech, its fullness, artistry and emotional expressiveness.

The construction of speech is determined by the structure, i.e. constructing phrases that make up speech

The fullness of speech depends on two points. The first is lexical sufficiency, which requires such a selection of words on the third, fourth, fifth, etc. positions in a phrase in which the thought would receive clear detection, disclosure. The second is the presence in a phrase of a certain number of semantic units. Too large (more than eleven) the number of semantic units makes the phrase inaccessible to understanding and memorization, which eliminates the need for the entire speech.

Artistry gives speech brightness, expressiveness, makes it extraordinary, colorful. Communicative speech is given artistry by the use of tropes: metaphors, epithets, comparisons, phraseological units, etc.

Emotionally expressive means of language include tempo, pauses, speech rhythm, and voice timbre. They allow you to highlight the main, essential things in speech and adapt it to the sound conditions. Auxiliary expressive means of communication are facial expressions and gestures. They enhance the impact of speech, make it dynamic and maintain long-term attention to the speaker.

The richness of the use of linguistic means in communication distinguishes a person favorably from those around him, creating reliable prerequisites for career advancement, leadership in social and professional activities, and internal psychological comfort.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Gee, James P. An Introduction to Human Language: Fundamental Concepts in Linguistics. New Jersey: Prentice Hall. 1993. Gorys, Keraf.1997. Komposisi. Ende-F

2. Kroeber dan Kluckhohn. 1952. *Culture, a critical Review of Concepts and Definitions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. Kramsch, Claire. 1998. *Language and Culture*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

3. Леонтьев А.А. *Язык, речь, речевая деятельность*. М.: Красандр., 1969. - 21с.

4. Мечковская Н.Б. *Социальная лингвистика*. М.Аспект пресс:, 1996. - 207 с.

5. Норман Б.Ю. *Теория языка. Вводный курс*. М.:Флинта, 2004. - С.296

6.Реформатский А.А. *Введение в языковедение*. М.: 1967. - С.536